

editor's comments

Signs of Confusion

When we see a red light by the side of the road, most of us understand that we should bring our cars to a stop. Confronted by somebody in tight leather pants and a muscle shirt, few of us conclude that we are dealing with an assistant professor of business administration or an aspirant to high political office. Both the red light and the leather pants communicate information, but only to those who are familiar with a particular system of traffic-signalling or an unspoken set of implications of particular styles of clothing. Such systems of meaning are relatively arbitrary, and totally culture-bound: there's no reason beyond the accidents of history that we might not have decided to use the color purple to convey the need to stop, or why bikers might not have ended up signalling their machismo with burnooses, or spandex tights, or button-down collars and narrow ties. Furthermore, much of what we communicate to each other we understand unconsciously: we do not need to have had a course in clothing to have come to understand the message of tight leather pants—and often, we know that meaning and act upon it without even realizing that we know it.

Semiology is the science of signs—the study of the codes by which we signify meanings to each other, and of the complex interrelated systems of signification that influence our perceptions and readings of reality. Zohar Shavit says that her purpose in her book *Poetics of Children's Literature* (University of Georgia Press) is to examine children's literature "as a system in a culture, or in other words, as a semiotic phenomenon" (177). Such an examination is long overdue, for there is no doubt that cultural assumptions are of enormous significance not just in determining the plots and themes of specific children's books, but also in our understanding of the phenomenon of children's literature as a whole—indeed, in the very fact that we even have such a thing as a special literature for children. Exploring those assumptions is surely the central task for critics of children's literature; if we simply take them for granted and thus unconsciously accept their validity, we are not likely to arrive at a significant understanding either of children's literature as a whole or of any specific book. Consequently, the program Shavit proposes for herself demands that her book be given careful and detailed consideration.

Literature is itself a system of signification, and a highly complex one: we read any given book in terms of an intricate set of assumptions about why we read, about how to read different sorts of books in different ways, about genre and symbol and plot and character. Furthermore, literature is merely one part of the larger system of signification, the culture that produced it; we understand the behavior of characters and the implications of settings in novels only in terms of societal assumptions about the potential meanings of such things as places and the way people behave. Shavit calls this complex configuration of intersecting significations a "polysystem"; her object, then, is to determine how children's literature relates to the polysystem, and how its relationships with the larger system work to produce its distinct characteristics. As she says, "How children's literature manages to function in such a complicated net of systems is acutally the core of the book; it is practically what it is all about" (180).

Its being about that leads Shavit to ask a series of questions:

1. How is literature intended for children different from other sorts of literature?

2. How do our attitudes toward both the functions of literature and the nature of childhood account for these differences?

3. Why do most people involved in the production of literature—publishers, editors, reviewers, even writers—consider children's literature to be inferior to other sorts of literature? To use Shavit's term, why does children's literature have such a "poor self-image"?

4. Why are there different kinds of children's literature (specifically, what we consider to be "good" children's literature, which Shavit calls "canonical" as opposed to "non-canonical" or popular literature)? How and why are they different from each other?

These are all good questions. Unfortunately, Shavit believes that nobody before her has ever bothered to ask them and claims that, while "important work has been done, notably in the compilation of national histories of children's literature," scholars of children's literature have ignored recent trends in literary study: "instead of applying the latest achievements in literary scholarship (in both the Eastern and Western worlds) to this new field, most scholars have preferred to study children's literature strictly within the context of traditional and overworn questions" (x).

Now anyone who reads the *Quarterly* and other journals devoted to children's literature knows that is simply not true. In the last decade, many scholars have indeed been examining exactly the questions that Shavit says have been ignored. To name just a few: Jack Zipes, Anita Moss, Jacqueline Rose, and Nancy Huse have explored some of the relationships between societal assumptions and children's literature. Aidan Chambers, Peter Hunt, Rod McGillis, Adrienne Kertzer, and Phyllis Bixler have investigated various aspects of the idea of the implied reader in children's literature, and Marilyn Cochran-Smith and Diana Kelly-Byrne have investigated children's reception of narratives. Jon Stott, Lois Kuznets, and Janice Alberghene have addressed the relationship between children's literature and the patterns of popular literature. Stephen Roxburgh, Patricia Dooley, myself, and others have explored the semiotics of picture books. There have been MLA sessions and articles in the *Quarterly* dealing with the relationships between children's literature and aspects of literary theory like structuralism, narrative theory, and canon formation.

But Shavit seems to be unconscious of most of this work; and that is a pity, for knowledge of it might have helped her to find her way past some of the glaring deficiencies of her own answers to the important questions she asks. It is sad to report that they are not as good answers as these good questions demand.

The most obvious deficiency of *Poetics of Children's Literature* is its inaccuracy. Sterling North, the author of *Rascal*, is referred to at one point as North Sterling. When I mentioned I was reading this book to a friend who specializes in early children's literature, she offered me a list of errors she'd noticed in the book while "flipping through it in ten minutes": Mary Ann Kilmer is called Mary Jane Kilmer, Maria Edgeworth is credited with writing *Little Goody Goosecap* (not hers and published when she was just twelve years old), James Janeway is called John Janeway, and so on. These factual errors signal some disregard for the exacting demands of scholarship based on historical

evidence. So does the distressing fact that Shavit depends so frequently on secondary sources like Sam Pickering's *John Locke and Children's Books in Eighteenth-Century England* for her descriptions of, and sometimes even her quotations from, early children's books; one begins to wonder if she has actually read those books. And what is one to make of her suggestions that a statement made in 1831 proves that fairy tales were considered bad for children in the early years of the nineteenth century, while a book published in 1823, eight years earlier, proves that this attitude was changing by the middle of the century? (76)

In fact, Shavit's theoretical statements are almost always based on brutal and unconvincing historical generalizations. She argues for a difference between simple children's books and "ambivalent" ones—those meant to be enjoyed differently by children and by sophisticated adults—on the bases of the supposed fact that in writing *The Nursery Alice*, Lewis Carroll "deliberately transformed it in order to appeal solely to children" (72); had she more accurately said "younger children," she could not have got away with suggesting that the sophisticated elements of the original *Alice* were intended solely for adults. Later, she bases the idea that in the early nineteenth century chapbooks were widely disseminated among poor adults who had no access to serious literature on a quotation that speaks of such people reading, not just chapbook tales and romances, but also more serious novels like *Tom Jones* and *Roderick Random*, which Shavit claims they did not know; and she says that religious books for children "lost their dominance" (173) after the first years of the nineteenth century, and thus disregards the countless thousands of Sunday School novels that were produced throughout the Victorian period, and that are, in fact, still being produced in huge quantities today.

Even more significantly, Shavit bases her entire reading of children's literature on what is surely a misunderstanding of Phillipe Aries' idea that childhood was thought of differently before the seventeenth century; she so misses the subtleties of Aries' argument (which has in any case been questioned by later scholars) that she asserts, "...until the seventeenth century children were not considered different from adults" (5). While there can be no doubt that adults in earlier times did not think of their children as we think of ours, it is ridiculous to assume they did not realize that these obviously shorter, more vulnerable, and less experienced people were not merely miniature versions of themselves: if nothing else, the high infant mortality rates of earlier centuries demanded a less involved attitude to youngsters than one could afford to have for older survivors. Shavit goes so far as to say that "the idea that children should be instructed by adults as far as their behavior was concerned" was "a notion unknown in Perrault's time (25); that ignores not just a whole body of instructional literature from the beginnings of recorded history, but also the fact that these adults had themselves somehow learned to behave in certain ways; they must have been taught to do so by someone who realized that they were ignorant enough to need to learn it.

The theories Shavit bases on such a superficial reading of history are doomed to be unpersuasive. The keystone of her argument about the peculiar nature of children's literature is the idea that Perrault's fairy tales, which begin children's literature as we know it, imply a double audience, naive children and sophisticated adults: "In this way, irony and satire signaled the highbrow adult, while the formulaic structures signaled the child reader" (15). The serious flaw in this argument is Shavit's own assumption that children are always naive and that only adults can appreciate irony. What is revealing about Perrault's tales is how they do in fact mix qualities that we have since come to identify as childlike on the one hand and adult on the other; in separating out elements that are in fact homogenized in Perrault, Shavit is merely applying twentieth century attitudes to children to seventeenth century text.

In fact, she reveals such biases throughout. Her conviction that people before the seventeenth century had no idea of childhood is merely a blindness to the possibility of any idea of childhood but her own; she blandly accepts "the increasing awareness of adults of the differences between themselves and children" (38) without considering that this "awareness"—or faith?—may also emerge from cultural assumptions. Speaking of the ambivalent position of children's writers, she says, "Society expects the children's writer to be appreciated by both adults...and children. Yet this demand is both complex and even contradictory by nature because of the different and even incompatible tastes of children and adults" (37)—a culture-bound assumption if there ever was one.

Furthermore, Shavit bases her central description of children's literature around this assumption: the idea that so called "good children's literature must appeal to two different audiences at the same time—to unsophisticated children, and also to the sophisticated adults who market and buy children's books. This results in children's books containing two different "models" or sets of narrative assumptions, each of which can be read independently of the other: one is the conventional formulaic story that gives pleasure to children, the other a more individualized literary construct that allows adults to think of the book as good literature:

What makes this double reading possible is the mutual exclusivity of the models structuring the text; it is as if one of the models, the more conventional, permits full realization without taking the other model into account, simply because the other model excludes it. In fact, the child reader is indeed supposed to ignore the less conventional model, while the interplay of the two models, the more and the less established, can be realized by adults only. (69)

This is an intriguing theory; and it does capture much of what is peculiar and interesting in children's fiction: its status as a product of adults intended for children, its mixture of pedagogy and entertainment, of formulaic plot and subtlety of style. Where the theory ceases to be persuasive is where it encounters Shavit's blithe assumption that children are incapable of understanding anything but simple formulas, and that therefore, the sophisticated elements in children's books can only be intended for and understood by adults. In fact, I would guess that it is a writer's assumption that children can indeed realize unconventional models that leads to the existence and production of most good children's books. In totally separating what supposedly appeals to children and what supposedly appeals only to adults, Shavit misses the most interesting characteristic of children's literature: the way in which the "models" are related to each other, the way in which the most characteristic children's books work to transform their audience from simple readers to more sophisticated ones.

The same blindness about the capabilities of children mars Shavit's discussion of the self-image of children's literature. She sees a series of comments in which children's writers claim seriousness for their work by denying that they write for children and asserting that they write for "the child within" as evidence for her idea that children's books contain many elements of no interest to children. She believes that these writers express disdain for their own craft when they deny that they write for children:

because of the poor self-image of children's literature, writer's attempt to liberate themselves from the children's system and wish to be considered as writers (or potential writers) for adults in order to better their position and to gain more freedom in their writing. The wish is manifested first in the writer's denial of a particular addressee (the child) and the denial of a distinction between writing for

adults and writing for children. . . . Not only does the outside world regard children's literature as inferior, but also the children's literature writers themselves do so, thus reinforcing and perpetuating this [poor] self-image. 6(41)

That is simply not true. In denying that they write for children, children's writers are merely trying to come to terms with the peculiar circumstances of their art; that, like all good writers, they write to please themselves, but that in some sense the genre they work in demands that they write for a childlike audience. What better solution to this problem than to talk about writing for the child within themselves? And how does the idea that writing for children might be considered as worthwhile as writing for adults imply disdain for children—unless we assume that children can't appreciate good writing? Once again, Shavit's blindness both to the capabilities of children and the ability of good children's books to educate their literary tastes causes her to miss the most interesting aspects of children's literature.

Shavit's inability to perceive the place of children's literature in literary education is a little surprising; one of the most persuasive aspects of her book is her discussion of how vast an influence pedagogical demands have on the nature of children's literature. She says, "The following universal can be proposed: unlike adult literature, canonized children's literature began to develop in response to the needs of the educational system, the result of which is the strong grip of the educational system on children's literature and the major part is plays in its formulation" (137).

True, I think, and not taken into account often enough in attempts to interpret the history and the nature of children's literature; but even here there are problems. Shavit suggests that this is a "universal" because she wants to assert that "the very same stages of development reappear in all children's literatures" (133). But if children's literature does indeed emerge from changing assumptions about children, then surely different culture's different assumptions would allow for different stages of development; and in fact, Canadian children's literature has developed quite differently from the British children's literature Shavit uses as a model, due to peculiar cultural pressures—and so, for that matter, has American children's literature. Indeed Shavit can only posit a "universal" through distortions of history. In separating out the development of what she calls "canonized" and "non-canonized" children's literature—the "good" as opposed to the popular—she totally ignores for an entire long chapter the way developments in one led to significant changes in the other. It does not help that she admits to this distortion only after having done it, when she says as the end of the chapter, "this scheme deliberately ignores, for methodological reasons, the function of popular literature in the development of children's literature" (157); what she never admits or seems to understand is that popular literature for children is unlike adult popular literature in that it almost always pays lip service to the formulaic pedagogical patterns of serious children's literature, and vice-versa—that the "canonical" and "non-canonical" actually share each other's qualities, in differing balances and for differing purposes, and that what they share is far more revealing than how they differ.

Finally, then, all of Shavit's potentially rewarding semiological investigations founder on the shallowness of her understanding of history and of her readings of children's books. Paradoxically, that shallowness emerges from her blindness to her own semiological assumptions: her failure to perceive her own unconscious attitudes. That's a pity—for I am convinced that a semiological approach to the phenomenon of children's literature as a whole is exactly what scholars of children's literature most urgently require. If we are to bring together the various insights and perceptions of the various critics I mentioned earlier, and also the detailed historical research of careful scholars like Sam Pickering and Mitzi Myers, into a

framework that will genuinely increase our understanding of children's literature—and above all, help us to introduce it to children—then what we need is an accurate and searching exploration of, as Shavit says, "the interrelations between literary and social constraints that create the history, inventory and structure of children's literature" (179-80). Unfortunately, *Poetics of Children's Literature* is not that accurate and searching exploration. Because it tries to be, it is an important book. But it is not a good one.

Perry Nodelman

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